

₹15,564 /ha, respectively [3,7]. Therefore, researchers have developed small-scale power threshers for small farmers. The total labour requirement and cost of operation in manual crop cutting, collecting and power threshing together vary from 252 to 272 man-h./ha, ₹12,451 /ha to ₹13,076 /ha [3,6]. The energy requirement of spike tooth type power thresher was 3.5 to 5 kWh/t grain [8]. To reduce the energy requirement, the amount of straw fed to the thresher can be reduced. Therefore, scientists have developed a direct-threshing type harvester, which can also be used by small-scale farmers [9]. It was an energy-saving method because only the crop ear-head was threshed instead of the whole crop. Also, the grain cleaning units dealt with less load. The machine components also reduced and thus the initial investment. Moreover, the operation of a lightweight harvester is more convenient. Such small-scale harvesters after some modifications were tested by different researchers. A commercial model power thresher “Yanmar DB 1000” fitted with a 4-kW diesel engine was tested at cylinder speeds of 200, 400 and 600 rpm [10]. It was tested with Amankwati paddy variety at 16.9 to 18% grain moisture content. They recommended cylinder speed and feed rate of 600 rpm and 400 kg/h, respectively, to get the best output capacity, threshing efficiency, grain loss, and energy consumption as 158.4 kg/h, 95%, 5.86% and 4.16 kWh/t of grain, respectively. The power thresher has a high throughput rate and therefore, requires less labour and time. It produces clean grain, which is not possible in manual and pedal threshing. The researchers evaluated the performance of a 1360 mm wide mini combine harvester that had 16-kW power (model 4LZ-1.0) [10]. Paddy crop varieties IR841 and Nerica L20 were harvested at forward speeds of 2.1 to 4.46 km/h. Proportionally, the grain throughput rate and harvesting capacity were reported to increase from 350 to 1515 and 500 to 3160 kg/h and 0.10 to 0.39 ha/h, respectively. The average fuel consumption for the corresponding throughput rate was 7.13 and 9.05 l/ha. The

labour requirement and estimated cost of operation were 8 man-h/ha and ₹6984 /ha, respectively. It can be said that in a combine harvester, the field capacity and throughput rate can be increased by increasing the forward speed. Ergonomically, a self-propelled mechanical harvester requires less human effort but is not affordable for small farmers. Therefore, the objective of this study was to develop a low-cost small-scale machine that can directly thresh the panicles. The field model and prototype were developed and tested in field conditions.

Materials and methods

Development and testing of single-row field model

The single-row model harvester was developed using optimized values of cylinder speed and plant feeding speed to validate the threshing performance of laboratory model. The components of field model harvester were threshing cylinder, concave, collecting tray, plant guiding plates, mainframe, ground wheels, engine, power transmission units and instruments. The whole components were mounted on the mainframe, which was supported on three wheels. Two wheels of 30 cm diameter were fixed 180 mm apart on a common axle with the frame below the rear end of cylinder. Another wheel was fixed below the front end of cylinder. The power was transmitted to the rear axle only. The optimized speed on wheel was attained through appropriate belt pulley, worm gearbox, and chain sprocket transmission. A dog clutch was provided at the wheel axle to connect and disconnect the power when required. The torque transducer and rotary encoder were installed on the field model to measure the threshing torque and cylinder speed, respectively. The input power was given to the sensors using a 12 V DC battery. The output of sensors was connected to different channels of the data logger, which transmits the data to the laptop. The laptop was installed with interfacing software CATMAN Easy to read data logger outputs. The transmission system and arrangement of instruments are shown in the Photograph in Fig 1.

1. Engine, 2. Crankshaft, 3. & 9. V-belt transmission, 4. Torque transducer, 5. Bellows coupling, 6. Transmission shaft, 7. Flexible jaw coupling, 8. Threshing cylinder, 10. Worm and pinion gearbox, 11. Chain sprocket transmission, 12. Dog clutch, 13. Ground wheel, 14. Rotary encoder
Fig 1- Power transmission and instruments of single-row direct ear-head model harvester

To test the field model, the crop was cultivated in a plot of 10×10 m area. The row and plant spacing was adopted as 25 and 15 cm, respectively. The testing was carried out on 93rd day after transplanting. Initially, the minimum height of grain-bearing portion from the ground level was measured. Accordingly, the axis height of threshing cylinder was set. The harvester was set parallel to the crop row. The clutch was pressed to disconnect the wheel's power. The engine was started and run idle at the rated speed of 3600 rpm to settle at a constant cylinder speed. The clutch was released to transmit the power on wheels. The machine started to move forward at a designed speed. The time taken to travel the 10 m length of crop row was measured using a stopwatch. The forward speed of operation was calculated. The machine was directed through handles. After operating one row, the threshed mixture collected in the collecting tray was taken out and analyzed. The grains, which shattered on the ground and remained on the plants after threshing were picked manually and weighed separately. The output of torque transducer and rotary encoder was analyzed.

Development and testing of prototype single-row harvester

The components of prototype harvester were the same as that of single-row field model harvester. The torque sensor and rotary encoder were not installed in the prototype. The cylinder shaft was connected with the 3.7 kW engine crankshaft through the intermediate shaft and v-belt transmission as shown in Fig. 2. After construction of PSRH, it was tested on the research field of IIT Kharagpur. A plot area of 30×20 m was prepared and 23-days-old paddy seedlings were transplanted following general cultivation practices. The crop was harvested after 93 days of transplanting following the headland pattern. The total time taken to harvest 600 m² area was recorded using the stopwatch. The effective field capacity was calculated. The fuel consumption was measured following the standard top-up method.

Fig. 2- Photograph of the prototype single-row harvester

Results and discussion

Field model performance and comparison with laboratory model

The optimized speeds of cylinder (V_p) and plant-feeding (V_f) for laboratory model were 18.94 m/s and 0.80 km/h, respectively, at which the threshing efficiency (η_{th}), specific energy (E_{th}) and total grain loss (L_{gt}) were 98.99%, 1.59 kWh/t and 4.84%, respectively [11]. For field model, V_p and V_f were 18.03 m/s and 0.65 km/h, respectively, which were lower by 3.79% and 16.67% than the optimized values. The forward speed was low in field conditions because of wheels slippage on soil. The threshed mixture, un-threshed grain, shattered grain and unstripped collected from the different sources were weighed. These values are given in Table 1. The torque and time required to thresh the 10-meter crop row were measured by the torque transducer. The curve plotted between time and torque is shown in Fig. 3. In Fig. 3, the different periods can be identified: period t_0 to t_1 (0 to 7.02 s) – idle load, period t_1 to t_2 (7.02 to 10.33 s) – increasing load, period t_2 to t_3 (10.33 to 59.69 s) – uniform load, period t_3 to t_4 (59.69 to 61.20 s) – decreasing load, and period t_4 to t_5 (61.20 to 64.80 s) – idle load. The time between t_1 (7.02 s) and t_4 (61.20 s) was the duration at which the threshing occurred. The time duration between 10.33 and 59.69 s was period of uniform threshing load. The average torque at this period was calculated and is given in Table 1.

The threshing efficiency, specific energy consumption and grain loss were calculated using the values given in Table 1. These are 98.23%, 3.42 kWh/t and 4.75%, respectively. The threshing efficiency and total grain loss were 0.66 and 1.88 % lower than the predicted values. The probable reason was high moisture content of the plants during field testing. During the laboratory experiment, the average moisture content of grain and straw was 14.48 and 28.32%, respectively. In the field experiment, it was 22.26% and 38.45%, respectively. Grain adheres more strongly with the plant stems at high moisture content. Probably for the same reason, the total grain loss was less in the field conditions. The shattering of grains was less at high moisture content. The energy consumption increased in the field by 115%. The separation of grains requires more force when the plants have more moisture content and thus more energy is required. The grain-to-straw ratio was different in the field. The throughput rate during the field testing was low because of low forward speed of travel. The specific energy consumption is expected to increase with a decrease in grain throughput rate. In the laboratory testing, only one-meter length of crop row was threshed at a time and there was less accumulation of the plant residue in the threshing chamber. In the field, length of crop row was 10 meters and more amount of plant residue had accumulated in the cylinder. The accumulation of straw may increase the aerodynamic resistance of cylinder. The prototype harvester was tested in the field conditions.

Fig. 3- A typical curve showing the variation in threshing torque concerning the time

Table 1- Test results of field model harvester operated in the field.

Measured values for field model harvester													
Sl. no.	Cylinder speed, (V_p), m/s	Forward speed (V_f), Km/h	Weight of material collected after threshing, (g)										Torque at uniform feed rate (T_{th}), Nm
			Threshed mixture in tray, (W_m)	Total grain in tray (W_{gct})	Clean grain in tray (W_{gc})	Damage grain in tray, (W_{gb})	Un-threshed grain in tray, (W_{gu1})	MOG in the tray, (W_{mog})	Un-threshed grain in the threshed plants, (W_{gu2})	Shattered grain (W_{gs}),	Total grain loss (W_{glt}),	Total grain-fed (W_{gf}),	
1	18.08	0.6511	1246.83	1134.8	1132.3	0.00	2.48	111.9	16.43	36.54	55.45	1187.8	1.23
2	18.05	0.6478	1332.87	1183.2	1180.0	0.00	3.21	149.6	22.13	40.84	66.18	1246.2	1.49
3	17.97	0.6516	1298.57	1210.7	1208.9	0.00	1.86	87.7	19.35	32.76	53.97	1262.8	1.47
Avg.	18.03	0.65	1292.76	1176.2	1173.73	0.00	2.52	116.40	19.30	36.71	58.53	1232.27	1.40
Calculated values for field model harvester													
Sl. no.	Cylinder speed, (V_p), m/s	Forward speed (V_f), km/h	Threshing efficiency (η_{th}), %	Percentage of clean grain (η_c), %	Threshing power, (P_{th}), kW	Grain throughput rate, (q) kg/h	Specific energy consumption, (E_{th}), kWh/t on	Total un-threshed grain in tray (L_{uth}), %	Shattered grain (L_{gs}), %	Total grain loss, (L_{gt}), %			
1	18.08	0.651	98.41	95.33	0.246	82.60	2.99	1.59	3.08	4.67			
2	18.05	0.647	97.97	94.69	0.299	79.55	3.75	2.03	3.28	5.31			
3	17.97	0.651	98.32	95.73	0.294	83.48	3.52	1.68	2.59	4.27			
Avg.	18.03	0.650	98.23	95.23	0.279	81.88	3.42	1.77	2.98	4.75			
Laboratory model harvester													
1	18.94	0.80	98.99	NA	NA	NA	1.59	NA	NA	4.85			

Table 2- Threshing efficiency, percentage of clean grain and grain loss of prototype single row harvester (PSRH).

Sl. no.	Cylinder speed, (V_p), m/s	Forward speed of machine (V_f), km/h	Threshing efficiency (η_{th}), %	Percentage of clean grain (η_c), %	Total un-threshed grain in tray (L_{uth}), %	Shattered grain (L_{gs}), %	Unstripped grain loss (L_{gu2}), %	Total grain loss, (L_{gt}), %
1	18.06	0.62	98.14	95.00	0.17	3.14	1.68	5.00
2	18.00	0.64	98.00	94.64	0.18	3.37	1.81	5.36
3	18.04	0.63	97.99	94.83	0.19	3.16	1.82	5.17
Avg.	18.03	0.63	98.04	94.82	0.18	3.22	1.770	5.18

Performance of prototype harvester

The performance of prototype single-row harvester (PSRH) is given in Table 2. The prototype harvester produces 98.04% threshed grain with 84.42 kg/h throughput rate, 0.014 ha/h effective field capacity at a forward speed of 0.63 km/h. Its fuel consumption was 0.27 l/h. The total grain loss was 5.17%, including 2.98% shattered grain. The estimated cost of operation and labour-time requirement were 71 man.h/ha and ₹99 /h (₹7022 /ha), respectively. The PSRH produces threshed material that contains 95.23% clean grain and 4.77% impurities. The grains were cleaned manually. During cleaning, labour time requirement was determined as 12 man-h/ha. The PSRH does not cut the residue during threshing. For cutting, collecting and transporting the residue 95 man-h/ha was required. The total labour and cost invested for crop threshing with PSRH, grain cleaning and residue-cutting operations together were estimated as 178 man-h/ha and ₹10,377 /ha, respectively.

Comparison of PSRH with different methods of crop cutting and threshing.

The performance of a few common methods of paddy harvesting was reviewed. Based on the available data, the cost of operation was estimated for these methods. The cost of operation and labour requirement of existing and proposed harvesting methods were compared using a bar chart shown in Fig. 4. It is depicted that 58% of labour could be saved by using PSRH over manual methods (M_1). Net saving in cost of operation was 22%, which is ₹2,977 /ha. The grain loss was also less. It can be stated that the prototype single-row harvester needed less labour time and was more economical. The operation of the PSRH was ergonomically more comfortable since the operator remained in an erect posture. Compared to the method where pedal thresher (M_2) was employed for threshing labour and cost-saving of 55.72% and 32%, respectively in PSRH. Compared with the power thresher (M_3), a labour-saving of 32% and cost-saving of 18.70% could be achieved. It can be

concluded that by using PSRH, the labour dependency can be reduced and the timeliness of harvesting could be improved. The input cost could also be reduced considerably. Compared to a mini combine harvester (M_4) the labour and the cost were higher with negligible difference in grain loss in PSRH. However, the initial cost of a mini combine harvester is ₹4,50,000, which is almost 11 times higher than the cost of PSRH. The small and marginal farmers cannot own it. Looking at the above facts it could be concluded that the PSRH could be recommended for small and marginal farmers. The grains could be harvested directly *in situ* in a short time compared to the manual method.

M_1 = Manual cutting, gathering, hand beating threshing and grain cleaning., M_2 = Manual cutting, gathering, threshing using pedal thresher and manual cleaning., M_3 = Manual cutting, gathering and threshing using power thresher. M_4 = Harvesting using mini combine harvester. M_5 = Harvesting using PSRH, manual grain cleaning and straw cutting.

Fig. 4- Cost of operation and labour-time requirement of different harvesting methods

Conclusions

The model and prototype single-row harvester were developed considering the optimized cylinder speed of 18.94 m/s and forward speed of 0.8 km/h. The model harvester was equipped with a torque transducer and rotary encoder to measure the threshing torque and cylinder speed. Its cylinder and ground wheels were

powered by a 3.7 kW petrol engine. Its forward speed was 0.65 km/h, which was slightly lower than the designed value due to the slippage of ground wheels. The field capacity, threshing efficiency and total grain loss were 0.014 ha/h, 98.23% and 4.75%, respectively at the grain throughput rate of 82 kg/h. The specific energy consumption was 3.42 kWh/t of grain, which was 115% higher than that of the laboratory model probably because of the high moisture content of the crop in the field. Based on the performance of the model single-row harvester, its prototype was developed. It had a forward speed of 0.63 km./hand field capacity of 0.014 ha/h. The threshing efficiency, total grain loss and fuel consumption were 98.04%, 5.17%, and 0.27 l/h, respectively. The estimated cost of operation of the prototype harvester was ₹99 /h or ₹7022 /ha. Including, crop threshing, cleaning and residue cutting, the labour and cost can be saved by 249 man-h. /ha and ₹2100 /ha, respectively, using PSRH in comparison to manual harvesting. While comparing the manual crop cutting and power threshing together these could be saved by 74 to 94 man-h/ha and ₹2,084 /ha to ₹2,709 /ha, respectively, using PSRH. It was concluded that the PSRH can be used by small and marginal farmers having land below 2 ha. The minimized labour, cost and grain loss over conventional methods are the reasons. In adverse conditions, quick harvesting using PSRH would reduce the grain loss that might take place when sudden rain occurs. For the above reasons, the PSRH is recommended for small and marginal farmers. It can be utilized to harvest paddy crops more quickly, protecting them from unfavourable weather situations.

Application of research: The machine can be used for direct threshing of paddy without cutting the plant. The researchers may use the *in-situ* data on torque and energy consumption.

Research Category: Direct threshing.

Abbreviation:

PSRH: Prototype Single Row Harvester

RPM: Rotations per minute

₹: Indian New Rupees

MOG: Material other than grain

V_p : Cylinder speed, (m/s)

V_f : Forward speed of machine (km/h)

η_{th} : Threshing efficiency (%)

η_c : Percentage of clean grain. (%)

L_{uth} : Total un-threshed grain in tray (%),

L_{gs} : Shattered grain (%),

L_{gu2} : Unstripped grain loss, (%),

Acknowledgements/Funding

The author conducted this research in the Department of Agricultural and Food Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur in India. The technical team of the lab and field helped in development and testing. This research received no specific grant from any funding agency, commercial or not-for-profit sectors

Authors' contribution: All authors equally contributed

Author's Statement: All authors read, reviewed, agreed and approved the final manuscript. Note-All authors agreed that- Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to publish/ enrolment

Ethical approval: This article does not contain any studies with human participants or animals performed by any of the authors.

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